

Energy Storage Design and Integration in Power Systems by System-Value Optimization

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Renewable generators are becoming cheap!

When it's dark and calm -> Need for energy storage

Photo by Jason Blackeye on Unsplash

Problem: Energy storage are still expensive

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Solution: Increase affordability of energy storage!

Investment Decisions using Electricity System Models

[3] Objective: minimise the total system cost that consist of

- investment costs in new generation projects
- investment costs in new storage capacity
- investment costs in new transmission line projects
- variable costs, such as costs for fuels or maintenance

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize}_{G,H,F,g,h,e} AC = & \left[\sum_{i,r} (c_{i,r} \cdot G_{i,r}) + \sum_I (c_I \cdot F_I) + \sum_{i,s} (c_{i,s}^{store} \cdot H_{i,s}^{store} + c_{i,s}^- \cdot H_{i,s}^- + c_{i,s}^+ \cdot H_{i,s}^+) \right. \\ & \left. + \sum_{i,r,t} (o_{i,r} \cdot g_{i,r,t} \cdot w_t) + \sum_{i,s,t} ((o_{i,s}^+ \cdot h_{i,s,t}^+ + o_{i,s}^- \cdot h_{i,s,t}^-) \cdot w_t) + \sum_{i,s,t} (o_{i,s}^{store} \cdot e_{i,s,t} \cdot w_t) \right] \end{aligned}$$

Power System of India @ PyPSA-Earth

Introduction
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Improving System Modelling with Energy Storage
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Applied Energy Storage System-Value Optimization
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Conclusions
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Research Questions

Part	Research Questions	Answers
Improving System Modelling with Energy Storage		
Applied Energy Storage System-Value Optimization		

Part I. Improving System Modelling with Energy Storage

1. Can energy system models be easily applied everywhere around the world?
2. How to avoid unintended storage cycling?

Solution: New PyPSA-Earth model **enables** easy use everywhere

⇒ Model is later used for energy storage research

Some novelties:

- Implements GIS-tagged & hourly data
- Implements new OpenStreetMap grid data
- Implements new network meshing strategies
- Validated in Africa
- ...

Part I. Improving System Modelling with Energy Storage

1. Can energy system models be easily applied everywhere around the world?
2. How to avoid unintended storage cycling?

Solution: Variable costs **removes** unintended storage cycling

Insights:

- The effect is a "software problem" not observed in reality
- If costs are **too low** = not working
- If costs are **too high** = model distortions
- Good values exists, but depends on **solver tolerance**

⇒ I provide a list of recommendations

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Introduction
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Improving System Modelling with Energy Storage
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Applied Energy Storage System-Value Optimization
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Conclusions
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Part II. Applied Energy Storage System-Value Optimization

3. How can storages be effectively designed and integrated in large energy systems?
4. What is the economic viability of different storage?

Problem: Existing methods were not suitable to evaluate tech

- ⇒ Cost and profit methods missing **system signals** (e.g. from system modelling)
- ⇒ Existing system methods missing **competition signals** (- counterfactual scenarios)

Introduction
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Improving System Modelling with Energy Storage
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Applied Energy Storage System-Value Optimization
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Conclusions
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Solution: New "Market Potential Method"

Market Potential Indicator (=deployment) signals:

- **Where** technologies are valuable
- **How** technologies should be sized
- **When/if** technologies are valuable

Market Potential Criteria:

- Only optimized technologies contain system-value
- Higher optimized magnitude = more system-value

⇒ Apply across scenarios to reduce uncertainty

EU study demonstrates new method

Insights:

- **LCOS** is misleading
- **Flexible storage sizing** has sign. system value
- **H2 technology mix** can be useful

Part II. Applied Energy Storage System-Value Optimization

3. How can storages be effectively designed and integrated in large energy systems?
4. What is the economic viability of different storage?

Optimizing multiple storage with new method provides answers

Novelties

- Analysed system-value of 20 energy storage
- Applied in new PyPSA-Earth model
- Applied "lonely optimist" scenario to address uncertainty

Insights:

- Optimizing multiple technology is important
- Some technologies are valuable to the system
- Some technologies can be with certainty ignored

Conclusions

Research Questions

Part	Research Questions	Answers
Improving System Modelling with Energy Storage	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Can energy system models be easily applied everywhere around the world? 2. How to avoid unintended storage cycling? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yes. E.g. PyPSA-Earth 2. Parameterization of variable costs
Applied Energy Storage System-Value Optimization	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. How can storages be effectively designed and integrated in large energy systems? 4. What is the economic viability of different storage? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. New "market potential method" signals storage design and layout 4. Some storages identified as relevant and irrelevant: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⇒ Evaluate under competition ⇒ Depends on the system

Deliverables

- 3 x peer-reviewed journal articles as **main author**
- 1 x article in journal submission as **main author**
- 1 x open funding proposal for open source solvers as **main author**
- 7 x articles, conference papers, open letters as **co-author**
- 9 x open source research software packages to which **I contributed**

Research Impact

- Open-source solver benchmark and author of successful **>500k€ funding** proposal for HiGHS
- Open data letter with 74 signatures from **professionals in the field**
- Contributions to scientific open-source software **used by industry and research**
- Creation and co-operation of a research initiative with **>15 active developers/researchers**
- Creation of a non-profit spin-out in open energy planning with a **team of >8 people**

Thank you! I enjoyed the PhD journey :)

Fig. 1.: GitHub contributions from Monday to Sunday over the past 3.5 years.

Literature I

- [1] *World Energy Transitions Outlook 2022*. 2022. URL: <https://www.irena.org/Digital-Report/World-Energy-Transitions-Outlook-2022>.
- [2] Adam Hawkes Oliver Schmidt Sylvain Melchior and Iain Staffell. “Projecting the future levelized cost of electricity storage technologies”. In: *Joule* (2019). URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S254243511830583X>.
- [3] Maximilian Parzen, Hazem Abdel-Khalek, Ekaterina Fedotova, et al. “PyPSA-Earth. A new global open energy system optimization model demonstrated in Africa”. In: *Applied Energy* 341 (2023), p. 121096. ISSN: 0306-2619. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.121096>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261923004609>.
- [4] European association for the cooperation of transmission system operators (TSOs) for electricity. *Transmission System Map*. 2018. URL: www.entsoe.eu/data/map/.

References

Literature II

- [5] Maximilian Parzen, Martin Kittel, Daniel Friedrich, et al. “Reducing energy system model distortions from unintended storage cycling through variable costs”. In: *iScience* 26.1 (2023), p. 105729. ISSN: 2589-0042. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2022.105729>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2589004222020028>.
- [6] Maximilian Parzen, Fabian Neumann, Adriaan H. Van Der Weijde, et al. “Beyond cost reduction: improving the value of energy storage in electricity systems”. In: *Carbon Neutrality* 1.1 (July 2022), p. 26. ISSN: 2731-3948. DOI: [10.1007/s43979-022-00027-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s43979-022-00027-3). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43979-022-00027-3>.

References